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**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>**Research Article****A RESEARCH STUDY ON POST DURAL PUNCTURE
HEADACHE IN CHILDREN****¹Haleema Abbas, ²Dr. Sana Rafiq, ³Dr Waqas Ali Khan**¹Pakistan Institute of Medical Sciences, Islamabad²Tehsil Head Quarter Hospital Chak Jhumra³Shaikh Khalifa Bin Zayed al-Nahyan Medical and Dental College Lahore**Article Received:** May 2019**Accepted:** June 2019**Published:** July 2019**ABSTRACT****Objective:** To observe the post-dural puncture headache in children.**Place and Time of Study:** Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore from September 2017 to August 2018.**Methodology:** Postdural cut cerebral pain (PDPH) in youngsters has once in a while been enrolled; however, some ongoing examinations demonstrate that kids may likewise create migraine after the lumbar cut. We report two instances of PDPH that happened in male youngsters matured 6 years (20 kg) and 10 years (25 kg) who got subarachnoid obstruct under sedation for herniotomy utilizing 27 G Quincke spinal needle at L4-L5 space with 0.5% hyperbaric bupivacaine at a portion of 0.3 mg/kg. They created normal postural migraine after 24 hr and 48 hr separately. They were effectively made do with complete bed rest, constrained hydration, and espresso drink twice, oral analgesics; and were released uneventfully. We reason that now a day's spinal anesthesia is being utilized in kids and PDPH can happen in this populace which can be treated on the same lines as in grown-ups. We trust that guardians should be educated about PDPH as there is powerlessness of youngsters to verbalize this torment.**Keywords:** Postdural Puncture Headache, Pediatric Spinal Anesthesia, Complications of Spinal.**Corresponding author:****Dr. Haleema Abbas,**

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INTRODUCTION:

Lumbar cut (LP) is performed in youngsters for demonstrative tests, intrathecal prescriptions and for spinal anaesthesia [1]. Until the most recent decade, it was trusted that postdural cut migraine (PDPH) was an exceptional protest in youngsters, however late examinations featured that pediatric populace may create PDPH [2, 3]. The predominance of migraine might be belittled among youngsters since it is regularly difficult for them to express their cerebral pain and different grievances. Nonetheless, it is reported that kids matured 3 years or more established can portray their cerebral pain and significantly more youthful kids may hint at headache [3, 4]. On writing look, instances of PDPH in kids have not yet been accounted for from Indian subcontinent. We are detailing two instances of PDPH that happened after 24 hr in 6 years male and after 48 hr in a 10 years male tyke who got spinal anaesthesia for herniotomy and were effectively overseen. Etiopathogenesis, clinical highlights and line of treatment of PDPH in kids are likewise examined.

CASES REPORT – I:

In the wake of taking educated assent from guardians, a 6-year-old male kid measured 20 kg was taken for right-sided herniotomy. Preanesthetic examination and routine examinations were unremarkable. The patient was fasting since medium-term and was preloaded with 200 ml Ringer lactate. For premedication, midazolam 0.75 mg, glycopyrrolate 0.1 mg, ondansetron 2 mg i.v. were given. Checking included noninvasive circulatory strain (NIBP), electrocardiography (ECG) and heartbeat oximetry (SpO₂). Ketamine 30 mg i.v. was given (as sedation), to counteract any development of patient amid subarachnoid square (SAB). The right horizontal position was given with a pad (collapsed towel) under the shoulder. SAB was given playing it safe with 0.5% hyperbaric bupivacaine 6mg (1.2 ml) in L4-L5 interspace utilizing 27G Quincke spinal needle (spinocaine grown-up size) in a solitary endeavour. After SAB he was turned prostrate. The medical procedure went on for 60 min uneventfully. Amid medical procedure O₂ was given with venti mask; BP, HR and SpO₂ stayed in typical range and got absolute 400ml RL. Propofol mixture 50 g/kg/min were given for sedation. Toward the finish of medical procedure 50 mg diclofenac suppository was embedded per rectally. He was cognizant, complying with verbal directions and moved to the postoperative ward. On night round he was agreeable, imperative parameters were ordinary, demonstrated total

recuperation from spinal anaesthesia and were released (daycare medical procedure). On next morning (after around 24 hr of SAB), he revealed with the protest of moderate force migraine situated in frontal district, which was exasperated by sitting stance. On examination, it was discovered that aside from postural migraine, there was no related grumbling of spewing, neck inflexibility or restricting signs, and was analyzed as an instance of PDPH. He was conceded and quickly i.v. implantation of RL 500 ml was allowed more than 2 hours and was educated to take bounty with respect to fluids orally, espresso drink twice, tab. ibuprofen 200mg TDS, complete bed rest (without a pad for 24 hr). He was watched for next 48 hr and did not have any grumbling of cerebral pain; had the option to move charmingly and released home uneventfully.

CASE REPORT – II:

A 10 years old male kid of 25 kg, having right inguinoscrotal swelling was planned for herniotomy. In the wake of taking educated assent from guardians, he was given spinal anaesthesia similarly concerning past kid. SAB was given with 1.5 ml (7.5 mg) of 0.5% of hyperbaric bupivacaine utilizing 27 G Quincke spinal needle in L4-L5 space. The medical procedure went on for 60 min uneventfully; all out fluid gave was 450 ml of RL, essential parameters stayed typical. He was additionally released at night. On day third (after 48 hr of SAB), persistent whined of migraine in parieto-occipital district which irritated in sitting position and calmed by resting. He answered to specialist and was alluded to the anaesthetist. On examination, just cerebral pain was available with no related sign or side effect and was named as PDPH. He was treated on the same lines as portrayed in past case-1. After 48 hr he was permitted to ambulate and released uneventfully.

DISCUSSION:

Spinal anaesthesia in youngsters was first considered by August Bier in 1899. From that point forward spinal anaesthesia was known to be drilled for quite a while with a progression of cases distributed as right on time as in 1909-1910 [5]. After certain years, it fell into neglect as a result of the presence of different muscle relaxants and inhalational operators and was practically unused after World War II. In the most recent decade, spinal anaesthesia began being supported again by numerous focuses because of expanding information on pharmacology, security and observing in children [6]. By International cerebral pain society, PDPH is classified in the gathering of migraines because of low CSF weight. It is a cerebral pain that improves when the patient is recumbent and intensifies with sitting upstanding. Its

beginning is after a lumbar cut, and most happen inside the first 3 days following the procedure [7]. Patients, as a rule, have an objection of a throbbing or dull agony in a fronto-occipital circulation. Be that as it may, this agony can later sum up, with radiation into the interscapular locale. Any developments that expansion the intracranial weight, (for example, hacking, wheezing, stressing or visual pressure may compound side effects. Related indications may incorporate sickness, spewing, hurt or firmness in the neck. Visual changes (photophobia, diplopia, obscured vision) and sound-related changes (hyperacusis, vertigo, tinnitus, ataxia, hearing misfortune) are not uncommon [8]. With respect to of PDPH, footing hypothesis proposes that it is brought about by diligent spillage of CSF through a cut prompted dural lease that may result in the listing of mind and meninges, consequently causing footing on agony touchy structures. The vascular hypothesis proposes that loss of CSF initiates adenosine receptor straightforwardly causing compensatory widening of cerebral veins and venous sinuses bringing about stretching of torment delicate fibres in the cerebrum [9]. Nevertheless, if a patient grumbles of migraine after lumbar cut, the doctor ought not accept the analysis of PDPH, rather other differential conclusion like meningitis, focal venous sinus thrombosis (CVST), spinal hematoma, cortical cerebral venous thrombosis, intracranial subdural hematoma, amiable intracranial hypertension, migraine and caffeine withdrawal migraine ought to likewise be considered [10]. Rate of PDPH in grown-ups has been accounted for going from 5% to 30% [9, 10]; while a writing survey dissected 40 articles distributed on PDPH in kids between 2004-2016 and presumed that event of PDPH after lumbar cut in youngsters is rare [11]. But this is likewise evident that finding of PDPH in this age gathering is very diffifaction. Small et al. [12] revealed that among 97 kids who experienced LP under GA no youngster matured up to 10 years built up a cerebral pain (0%). Of the kids matured 10-12 yrs, 2 out of 17 built up a migraine (11.8%) and in kids matured 13-18 years 5 out of 10 built up a cerebral pain (half). The occurrence of PDPH is accounted for to be a few creases higher after indicative lumbar cut than after spinal anaesthesia [13]. This distinction was ascribed to enormous needle measure (20-22G) utilized in analytic punctures when contrasted with 25-27G utilized in pediatric spinal anaesthesia. Bigger needles cause a progressively serious spillage of CSF bringing about a higher rate of post-puncture symptoms [14]. After demonstrative lumbar cut, the occurrence of PDPH was accounted for to be 5-10% [15, 16]. Interestingly, PDPH rates after spinal anaesthesia are accounted for to be exceptionally low. Ahmed et al.

[16] watched no instance of PDPH among 78 kids (0%) matured between 2-6 years experiencing spinal anaesthesia with 25G Quincke spinal needle. Punuch et al. [17] additionally discovered that PDPH happened in just 5 kids among 1132 youngsters matured between a half year to 14 years (0.4%) after subarachnoid square. Ylonen et al. [1] announced that the rate of extreme PDPH which required epidural blood fix in kids was around 1 out of 750 spinal punctures for anesthesia with 25-27 G needles (0.1%). In our establishment, in a year on a normal 200 kids are given spinal anesthesia with 27G Quincke spinal needle for different medical procedures. Just these two cases were accounted for to us in the last five years for PDPH showing an exceptionally low rate of PDPH in kids after SAB. In grown-ups, the pencil point needle tip has been related with a lower frequency of PDPH. In an ongoing randomized trial [18] the occurrence of PDPH was 36% in the cutting needle gathering (Quincke, Atraucan) and 3% in the Whitacre gathering. Electron microscopy demonstrates that pencil point tip really causes more injury. It is speculated this expanded restricted injury may start an inflammatory response that advances mending at the cut site, [18] while in youngsters no distinction in frequency of PDPH was accounted for utilizing various sorts of needles (Quincke, Whitacre) and par aesthesia was watched all the more normally in the Whitacre gathering (10%) than in the Atraucan gathering (2%) [9]. Many crisis divisions still utilize the cutting needles, potentially on the grounds that the pencil point needles require more aptitude to utilize and might be related with a higher disappointment rate. We additionally utilized Quincke needle (27 G) in both of the cases. Treatment of PDPH in youngsters stays on a similar line as adults. First line treatment comprises of gentle analgesics, bed rest and constrained fluid treatment by mouth or intravenous route. Caffeine treatment bolsters the vascular hypothesis of PDPH, as it hinders adenosine receptors and along these lines goes about as a cerebral vasoconstrictor [19]. Cosyntropin is an adrenocorticotrophic hormone (ACTH) simple that invigorates the adrenal cortex to emit glucocorticoids, mineral corticoids and powerless androgens; it actuates adenyl cyclase with a resultant increment in intracellular cAMP. It expands CSF creation through a sodium dynamic transport instrument just as perhaps expanding beta endorphins in the CNS, with an ensuing increment in agony limit. The portion is 0.25-0.75 mg i.v., however, its utilization has not been depicted in children [20]. If the manifestations are not assuaged inside a couple of days it is sensible to consider

epidural blood fix with 0.2-0.3 ml/kg and was discovered powerful in youngsters also [1, 21, 22].

CONCLUSION:

We need to underline that however event of PDPH is uncommon in kids; it could be a difficulty that ought to be remembered after spinal anaesthesia. Guardians should be educated about this as youngsters may not verbalize it and confirmation ought to be given that it very well may be dealt with.

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